

DEVELOPMENT OF ALUMINIUM PROFILES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SOME MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FRESH INGOT AND RECYCLED SCRAP

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ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that there is an increasing cost associated with the procurement of Virgin (fresh) Aluminium ingots. It has become necessary to recycle scraps to meet most domestic and Industrial demand. This development can only receive approval if the mechanical performance of the scraps is scientifically proven. Samples for impact, Torsion and Tensile test were prepared, three each from scraps and ingots and were subjected to destructive standard impact, torsion and tensile testing. Result obtained during torsion shows for fresh ingots failure occurred at 0.98 Nm while for scraps, failure occurred at an average point of 1.04 Nm. For impact, strain energy of 17J was observed with fresh ingot and scrap was 18J. The tensile test showed ultimate strength of 1.85KN/mm² for fresh ingot and 1.80KN/mm² for recycled scrap. The result, although showing marginal differences suggest a mix outcome, indicating no significant difference between fresh Aluminium Ingots and recycle Scrap Aluminium.

KEYWORDS: Aluminium profile, Scraps, Ingot, recycle, destructive test and properties.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium, owing to its high strength to weight ratio and its peculiar corrosion resistance properties, has found wide usage in a diverse range of industries. It is a pivotal material in aviation, automobile, food and beverage, and to a great extent, the construction industries. This silver white metal obtained from Bauxite rock is the third most abundant element (after oxygen and silicon) and the most abundant on the earth crust (8% by mass) (Onuh, 2000).

According to Higgins (1993), the versatility of Aluminium is enhanced by some of its compelling properties. They include; high conductivity (it has 65% conductivity of copper), comparatively high resistance to corrosion, high malleability, can be recycled severally without losing its superior characteristics and it is relatively cheaper. It is the most used non-ferrous metal. The global production of Aluminium in 2005, for example, was 31.9 million tonne second only to iron at 837.5 million tonne (Wikipedia, 2009).

Aluminium can be obtained from primary source (Bauxite) or from secondary source (Recycled Scrap). The former is energy intensive and require a relatively cheap source of electricity thus making recycling imperative. In fact, Papp (1996) suggested that recycling is inevitable because “the reusable nature of metals contribute to the sustainability of their use”. Hence, recycling, a significant factor in the supply of any of the key metal used in our society provides environmental benefits in terms of energy savings, reduced volume of waste, and reduced emissions. These reductions, in turn, result in reduced disturbance of land, reduced pollution, and reduced energy use.

At the local scene, advocating for the use of recycled scrap aluminium cannot be done in the absence of scientific proofs that the mechanical properties of the recycled scrap is comparatively good or at par with fresh ingot. In justifying this effort therefore, it is important to place in the scientific domain, experimental facts that speak for or against recycling as an effective cost saving measure in the sourcing of aluminium product for industrial use. The aim and objective of this paper is to determine experimentally the comparative mechanical qualities of scrap aluminium with fresh ingot. It is envisaged that a positive outcome will make the case for recycling more forceful.

THEORY AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The analysis involves the production of sample (specimen) size from fresh Ingot and Recycle scrap for Torsion, Tensile and impact test. This is to help in the determination of Torsional rigidity, elastic and plastic behaviour and the toughness of both the fresh ingot and the recycle scrap. The samples are coded in the manner shown on Table 1.

Table 1: Test/Sample Code

S/NO	TEST/SAMPLE TYPE	1 ST SAMPLE	2 ND SAMPLE	3 RD SAMPLE
1.	Torsion/fresh ingot	TR/A1	TR/A2	TR/A3
	Torsion/Recycle Scrap	TR/B1	TR/B2	TR/B3
2.	Tensile/Fresh Ingot	TS/A1	TS/A2	TS/A3
	Tensile/Recycle Scrap	TS/B1	TS/B2	TS/B3
3.	Impact/Fresh Ingot	IM/A1	IM/A2	IM/A3
	Impact/Recycle Scrap	IM/B1	IM/B3	IM/B3

The Aluminium Fresh Ingot sample was prepared from Aluminium, 6061-T6 through a standard process of wooden pattern formation, fine sand ramming with appropriate fixture such as spruce, riser and cores. More precisely, the experimental procedure was accomplished using four different equipments, namely; an electric arc furnace, a torsion testing machine(see table2 and 3), an impact testing machine at two different location between the period of two month (June-August, 2008). Samples where placed in a melting trough of a *Fours Nagat* electric arc furnace (serial number 44550-*Montoir de Bretagne*, France) with capacity of 1200°C. Pouring was accomplished at 670⁰ C and after cooling casting was shaken off and sand blasted.

The process was repeated for scraps obtained from various source for the recycled Aluminium. Subsequent to which all the samples were machined to test sample size and shapes. These processes were accomplished in two locations namely, Federal Polytechnic Bauchi, and KAL Extrusion Limited, Bauchi.

TORSION TEST

In the testing machine the ends of the specimen are held in suitable grips through one of which the torque is applied, other is connected to the torque arm, by means of which the torque on the specimen is measured. The torque arm is attached to the indication unit electronically.

The angular movement of the straining spindle and holder is indicated on a large diameter protractor and venire which record deflection down to 0.1 degrees. Table 2 shows the specification for the torsion testing machine.

Table 2: Specification for Torsion Machine

NAME OF EQUIPMENT	TORSION TESTING MACHINE
Model	SM 1 MK 11
Type No	SM1
Serial No	367
Amps	12 amps
Volts	240V
Frequency	50 Hz
Phase	Single
Manufacturer	Tec. equipment limited Nottingham, England

According to Rajput (2009) the value of modulus of rigidity can be found out through observations made during the experiment by using equation 1.

$$\frac{T}{J} = \frac{G\theta}{L} \text{ ----- Eqn. 1}$$

- Where:
- T = Torque (Nm)
 - J = Polar moment of Inertia (m⁴)
 - G = Modulus of rigidity (GN/m²)
 - L = Gauge length (m)
 - θ = Angle of twist (radian)

TENSILE TEST

On this hydraulic tensile testing machine the original length of the specimen is noted before insertion unto the machine, where it is firmly gripped before gradual application of load. A digital meter, measures the load and the extension is also noted along side the change in diameter. More frequent readings are obtained as the specimen approaches the fracture point. The process continues to fracture point. Table 3: Shows specification for the tensile testing machine

Table 3: Universal material testing machine.

<i>Name of Equipment</i>	<i>Universal Material Testing Machine</i>
Model	SM 100
Serial Number	W6382/3
Capacity	100KN
Volts	240V
Amp	12amps
Frequency	50Hz
Phase	Single
Manufacture	Telequipment limited Nottingham, England.

The stress, σ is

$$\sigma = \frac{\text{load}}{\text{area}} \text{-----Eqn.2}$$

Strain, ϵ

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l_o} \text{-----Eqn. 3}$$

Young modulus, E

$$E = \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon} \text{-----Eqn. 4}$$

IMPACT TEST

The Wolpert pendulum impact testing machine was used to determine the toughness of the materials. The machine is provided with our analogue circular indicator to indicate the impact energy consumed during the test. A set back idle pointer (provided with a rotary button for zero adjustment) serves for indication of impact energy consumed during the test. The test indicates the toughness of a material, particularly its capacity for resisting mechanical shock.

The pendulum hammer is raised and it gets the potential energy.

$$AP = Fh \text{-----Egn. 5}$$

Where F = the weight of the pendulum
 H = height of rise of the hammer

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results obtained from the various test are shown in Table 4a&b, 5, and 6 for torsion, Tensile and Impact respectively.

Table 4a: Result of Torsion Test

Angle of Twist (Radian)	Torque (Nm)*					
	TR/A1,	TR/B1,	TR/A2,	TR/B2,	TR/A3,	TR/B3
0	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29
0.262	0.48	0.61	0.42	0.60	0.50	0.59
0.523	0.64	0.72	0.59	0.69	0.62	0.61
0.785	0.81	0.74	0.70	0.73	0.78	0.65
1.047	0.85	0.80	0.83	0.79	0.80	0.69
1.308	0.86	0.83	0.86	0.82	0.88	0.72
1.570	0.88	0.89	0.92	0.85	0.90	0.73
1.872	0.97	0.89	1.00	0.87	0.96	0.86
2.094	-	0.92	-	0.90	-	0.89
2.355	-	1.00	-	1.02	-	0.99
2.617	-	1.05	-	1.03	-	1.02

*see Table 1 for code

Table 4b: Failure mode under Torsion

Angle of twist of radian		Modulus of Rigidity*			
A1 (GPa)	B1(GPa)	A2(GPa)	B2(GPa)	A3(GPa)	B3(GPa)
57.5	73.0	56.0	71.9	59.9	70.7
38.4	43.2	35.4	41.4	37.2	36.6
32.4	29.6	28.0	29.2	31.2	26.0
25.5	23.9	24.8	23.7	23.9	20.7
20.6	19.9	28.6	19.7	21.1	17.0
17.6	17.2	18.2	17.0	18.0	14.6
16.6	15.2	16.5	14.9	16.5	14.2
-	13.8	-	13.4	-	13.3
-	13.3	-	13.6	-	11.9
-	12.36	-	12.4	-	11.2

*see Table 1 for code

Table 6: Impact Test Result

Sample*	Initial Value	Force (N)
IM/A1	180	17.63
IM/B1	180	18.13
IM/A2	180	16.75
IM/B2	180	17.86
IM/A3	180	16.67
IM/B3	180	18.00

*see Table 1 for code

Figure 1 shows the failure mode under torsion load of one of the sample, while Figure 2 shows the deformation (Elastic and plastic) characteristic of the fresh Ingot and recycled scrap.

On a broad scale, the data shows mix result. While isolated differences exist for the various test result, albeit marginally, significant disparity that may suggest a substantial difference in the mechanical performance of fresh Ingot of aluminium and recycle scrap Aluminium remains to be seen.

From the data obtained for elastic deformation of the samples in Table 5 and Figure 2, the fresh Ingot exhibited a comparatively good elastic behaviour and strain hardening characteristic with a mean young modulus of 107.26KN/mm². The recycle scrap tailed marginally behind with a fair behaviour and a mean Youngs modulus of 101.91KN/mm². These results are similar to result obtained in previous work on the effect of heat treatment on creep resistance of aluminium (Musa, 1996 and Onuh, 2000).

The ductility and resilience of the recycle scrap material is much better than the fresh Ingots. The trends are shown in Figure 1 as well as Table 4b. The mean modulus of rigidity for the recycle scrap is 71.8GPa while the fresh Ingot is 57.8GPa. These results, when compared with actual modulus of rigidity for Aluminium 6061-T6 which is 70GPa, according to Wikipedia (2009) indicate clearly that recycle scrap, because of the elevated alloys behaviour, test better under torsion.

The torsion behaviour pattern is replicated under the impact test where the recycle scrap gave a better performance with mean energy stored (indicating the degree of toughness) of 18.00J while the fresh ingot showed a mean energy storage value of 17.00J as shown in Table 6. The alloy element presence, even though not controlled, is responsible for the marginally higher level of toughness of the scrap.

CONCLUSION

Recycling scrap Aluminium blended slightly with fresh Ingot provides a stable material that does not change in any significant way from the primary element because the mechanical properties are similar to those of the primary element. And since the cost of sourcing primary element is slightly higher than the cost of recycling, a reduction in production cost can be achieved without any adverse effect on performance of the material in service.

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Table 5b: Tensile Test Result

<i>Load (N)</i>	<i>Length L_i (mm)</i>		<i>Extension D_i (mm)</i>		<i>Diameter (mm)</i>		<i>Area, A (mm²)</i>		<i>Stress T_e</i>		<i>Strain</i>	
	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>	<i>TS/A3</i>	<i>TS/B3</i>
0	91.0	91.0	0.00	0.00	11.00	11.00	95.03	95.03	0	0	0	0
20	91.2	91.2	0.20	0.20	10.41	10.68	85.11	89.58	0.2349	0.2232	0.00219	.00219
30	91.4	91.4	0.40	0.40	10.39	10.60	84.70	88.24	0.3541	0.3399	0.00439	.00439
50	91.6	91.6	0.60	0.60	10.35	10.50	84.13	86.59	0.5943	0.5774	0.00659	.00659
70	91.8	91.8	0.50	0.58	10.30	10.48	83.32	86.26	0.8401	0.8115	0.00549	0.00549
90	92.0	92.0	1.01	1.00	10.25	10.42	82.51	85.27	1.0907	1.0554	0.01109	0.01098
110	92.2	92.1	1.02	1.10	10.20	10.36	81.71	84.29	1.3462	1.3050	0.01120	0.01208
130	92.4	92.5	1.23	1.20	10.18	10.33	81.39	83.80	1.597	1.5513	0.01351	0.01318
150	92.6	92.5	1.20	1.28	10.17	10.27	81.23	82.83	1.846	1.8109	0.01318	0.01400

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